

Implementation and Recruitment Process of Employees at PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands

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ABSTRACT

This Research is carried out in the PT. PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands, the purpose of this research is to know the process of recruitment of power implemented in the PT. PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands. Data analysis in this research uses the qualitative descriptive results of the previous discussion, then the author can conclude that in the recruiting process of Power implemented at the level of Senior High School/Vocation Secondary School /level running well and in accordance with the process undertaken by the candidate employees until the employee is accepted as employee of the PT PLN (Persero). However, there are still empty posts in the Human Resource Development Unit section. This means that here there is an Empty post then the job of the post is done by the employees who are in the unit so that will make the achievement of the objectives of the company not achieved well and effectively.

PENDAHULUAN

A company needs a workforce of the highest quality. One of the main keys to creating effective and efficient human resources lies in the recruitment process. Recruitment is the process of job search to fill vacancies in a company. Recruitment is about meeting the needs of the workforce according to the number and qualifications, both in the short, medium and long term of the company.

PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands or often referred to as is one of the BUMN companies that deals with all aspects of electricity that exist in Riau and the Riau islands whose office is located in Pekanbaru City, in serving the community Pt PLN Riau Region and islands Riau needs a qualified human resources to carry out daily activities, both the human resources that work in the company as well as those working outside the company, as is the case in the recruitment of the executive power of the PLN, Riau region and the islands of Riau with care in obtaining new candidate employees who are professional and qualified in accordance with the needs of the company.

In the implementation of the recruitment of Senior high school / Vocation Secondary School / Sederajat PT PLN Centre gives authority to the PLN PT (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands to carry out recruitments. Recruitment the executives performed by PLN P (Persero) of Riau Province and Riau Islands is from external sources of the company such as open or public recruiting.

The implementation of open recruitment in the PLN (Persero) Riau Territory and Riau Islands is carried out online with announcement in the mass media/newsletters, website and live visits as well as socialization to the schools in the vicinity of Riau Province and the Riau island with no tribal, religious and racial conditions.

The PLN (Persero) Riau Region and the Riau Islands are only authorized in the recruitment of Senior High School / Vocation Secondary School/ equal level executive according to the majority required and have defined the respective fields of each employee such as Administrative field, DIS field, KIT field, and OPT field. On the Administration fields work in the office, DIS (Distribution) and KIT (Manufacturer) fields can work in offices and outside of offices, and the OPT (Operator) field works in the field.

In 2022, the recruitment of executive personnel for Senior High School / Vocation Secondary School//Equivalent level PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands divided two levels of admission, namely Level I admission of major areas required in Distribution, Manufacture and Administration and Level II admission major areas needed in Operators. The following is the number of executive staff received at the level of Senior High School / Vocation Secondary School/Equal Level I PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands as follows:

Table 1. Number of Recruitment of Executive Officers Accepted in Secondary High School/SMK/Equivalent Level I PT PLN (Persero) Riau Territory and Riau Islands

No	Education	Department	Major	Code	Amount
1	Senior High School				
	a. SMA IPA	Teknik	Distribusi	DIS	12
	b. SMA IPA	Teknik	Pembangkit	KIT	8
	Amount				20
2	Vocation School				
	a. SMK Listrik	Teknik	Distribusi	DIS	35
	b. SMK IT	Teknik	Distribusi	DIS	16
	c. SMK Mesin	Teknik	Pembangkit	KIT	15
	d. SMK Otomotif	Teknik	Pembangkit	KIT	14
	e. SMK Administrasi	Non Teknik	Administrasi	ADM	9
	f. SMK Kesekretariatan	Non Teknik	Administrasi	ADM	8
	Amount				97
	Total				117

Source: PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands

Table 2. Number of Recruitment of Executives Accepted at Senior High School Level /SMK/Equivalent Level II PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands

No	Education	Department	Major	Code	Amount
1	Senior High School				
	a. SMA IPA	Teknik	Operator	OPT	3
	Amount				3
2	SMK				
	a. SMK Mesin	Teknik	Operator	OPT	5
	b. SMK Elektronik	Teknik	Operator	OPT	7
	c. SMK Listrik / Elektro	Teknik	Operator	OPT	5
	d. SMK Teknik Bangunan	Teknik	Operator	OPT	4
	Amount				21
	Total				24

Source: PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands

Based on the data from the two tables above, the number of recruits of Level I executive staff for the distribution, manufacturing, and administration departments was 117 people and the level II executive recruitment for the Operator department was 24 people. The Department's position is categorized as an executive with a retirement age of 46. Placement throughout the Sumatera PLN regional working area with priority placement in the PLN PT (Persero) Riau Working Territory and Riau Islands. In order to obtain a new job candidate that meets the desired requirements, the new employment candidate must carry out the recruitment process phase by phase so that it obtains employees that meet the needs of the company with the specified requirements.

LITERATURE RESEARCH

A. Recruitment

Recruitment is the act or process of finding qualified labour and the quantity and type of labour required, withdrawal of labour relating to the satisfaction of labour needs according to the number and quality of labour, both in the short, medium and long term. Withdrawal is the activity of seeking and influencing the workforce in order to apply for vacant vacancies by the company "seeking" i.e. determining the resources of workforce to be pulled "influencing" is the establishment of the means of its withdrawals, such as through advertising on the time media and or through existing employees

Recruitment is a series of activities that seek and engage job seekers by motivating the skills, expertise, and knowledge required to cover the gaps identified in employment planning. From the above defence the author can conclude that recruitment is a process of finding employees or candidates to meet the human resources needs of an organization or company.

B. Recruitment Purpose

The objective of recruitment is to receive as many applicants as possible according to the company's qualifications and various resources, thus enabling to enlist potential employees with the highest quality and the best. In general, the purpose of withdrawal of labour is to satisfy labour requirements in accordance with the requirements of a job.

Specifically, the purpose of withdrawal of labour, among others:

1. To be in line with the company's program and strategy.
2. To determine labour needs in the short and long term, relating to changes in the company, human resource planning, employment plans, and employment analysis.
3. To support corporate policies in managing diverse human resources.
4. Helps in improving the success of the workforce assessment process by reducing potential employees who are not clearly eligible to become employees.
5. Reduce the likelihood of a new employee leaving.
6. In an effort to coordinate withdrawals with recruitment and employment development programmes.
7. Effective evaluation of the various techniques used in recruitment.
8. Meeting corporate activities to support government programmes in terms of reducing the unemployment rate.

C. Recruitment Resources

In order to meet the job needs, there are two sources of recovery of labour that can be done:

1. There are various reasons for attracting the workforce from within the company, among others:
 - a. As an incentive to prepare for relocation or promotion of office, to raise the morale of the workforce and to appreciate employees who have achieved work.
 - b. Knowing the personality, abilities and skills of employees more deeply than attracting employees from outside the company requiring a withdrawal process.
2. There are various ways to accept employees from outside the company: Advertising in time media, trade unions, government agencies, educational institutions, other companies from the Internet.

D. Recruitment Process

The process of recruiting a good employee is as follows:

1. Basic determination of recruitment: The withdrawal policy of a candidate employee must be established in advance so that the applicants who enter their application correspond to the job or position they are seeking. Job specifications must be detailed and clear so that applicants know the qualifications required by the vacancy.
2. Determination of Recruitment Resources: Once the specifications of the required employee's work are known, sources of potential employee withdrawal must be determine
3. Methods of Recruitment: The recruitment method will have a major influence on the number of applications that enter the company. The method of recruiting potential new employees is the closed method and the open method.

METHOD

A. Types and Data Sources in this Research:

The research was carried out in PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands, which is located in the path Pekanbaru-Riau.

1. Primary Data Primary

Data is the type of data collected by the author obtained directly from the source of the data, such as interviews with the parties involved in this reporting on the PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands.

2. Secondary Data

Secondary data is data obtained indirectly through an intermediary or acquired and recorded by another party. Secondary data is generally evidence, records or historical reports that have been assembled in a published archive and that have not been published. Like information about the company's history, organizational structure and the sponsorship books that support this reporting.

B. Data Collection Methods

1. Observation

Oservation is the collection of data carried out by the author by observing directly objects that are problematic in the implementation of the recruitment process of the PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands.

2. Interview

Data collection carried on by the writer by conducting queries and accountability to the parties related to the reporting.

3. Documentation

Documentation is a technique used to retrieve the necessary data based on the company's regulations, the development of employees related to the problems that have become the object of observation in order to supplement the required data. The data collected by the author with this technique are documents relating to PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands, such as Company Profiles, Organizational Structure and Employee Data.

C. Data Analysis

Descriptive methods, in which in this method attempts to describe and describe the conditions occurring on the object of research based on the data gained, then analyzed on the basis of relevant theories, and then can draw a conclusion

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Recruitment Resources

PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands is a BUMN company operating in the field of electricity, which manages the electricity aspects that exist in Riau and the Riau Islands. Riau Province and Riau Islands use recruitment sources that come from external companies. In carrying out external recruitments, Riau Region and Riau Islands use open or general recruiting for the level of Senior High Schools/Vocation School.

Open Recruitment is recruitment that is carried out openly or publicly through announcements in the mass media/newsletters, websites and live visits as well as socialization to schools in the vicinity of the PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands without requiring tribe, religion and race. Open recruitment is like:

1. Education institutions The education institutions are one of the parties that cooperate with the company in order to educate and develop the potential of science they learn in the vocational secondary school that exists in the environment of PT PLN (Persero) Riau Province and Riau Islands.
2. Labour Market of PLN (Persero) Riau Territory and Riau Islands in recruitment of executives using the labour market to hold a meeting between job seekers with the PLN (Persero).

Process of Recruitment of Power Executives in PLN (Persero) Riau Territory and Riau Islands. The main objective of the recruitment process is to get the right new workforce, for a particular position so that the person is able to work optimally and can survive in the company for a long time.

The recruitment process is carried out by PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands to obtain new employees who meet the requirements specified by the PLN Region through the process of selection such as Administrative Selection, Endurance Test, Academic Test, Psychotic Test, Physical Health Test and Surrogate Test (Laboratory), Interview Test, and Priority Diploma, until the employees are accepted as employees of PLN Riau Province and Riau Islands.

The recruitment process for PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands is as follows:

1. Location of recruitment.

The establishment of the recruitment location of the executive is determined by the PLN (Persero) Central Office, through a letter of duty given to the Main Office designated by the Central Office for the place of implementation of recruiting.

2. Formation of the Recruitment Team

After the establishment of the place of execution of the next step, namely the formation of the recruitment team, the people or teams appointed to undertake and oversee the course of the process, the teams designated by the PLN (Persero) PT of Riau Territory and Riau Islands have the qualification in carrying out the task of recruiting the executive force.

3. Coordination Meeting

The PLN (Persero) of Riau Region and Riau Islands is to hold a coordination meeting on the implementation of recruitment of executive force starting from making and determining the Cost Budget Plan necessary for the execution of the recruiting process starting from the publication, the place of enforcement and the tests carried out in such recruitments.

4. Announcement of Admission of Officers

Announcements of admission of officials by PLN (Persero) Riau Territory and Riau Islands recruitment is open to Senior High School/Vocation Secondary Equivalent level online through social media, and print media website, as well as timetable and place of selection will be announced www.pln.co.id/ riau and www.ecc.ft.ugm.ac.id.

Table 3. Announcement of Recruitment of Power Suppliers Level Senior High School/Vocation Secondary School /Equivalent Stage I 2016 PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands

No	Department Position	Departement	Code	Education Conditions
1	Teknik	Distribusi/ Transmisi	DIS	SMA IPA, SMK Listrik, SMK IT
2		Pembangkit	KIT	SMA IPA, SMK Mesin, SMK Otomotif
3	Non Teknik	Administrasi	ADM	SMK Administrasi, SMK Kesekretariatan

Source: PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands

1. Administration Selection

Administrative selection is a test to filter employees who meet the requirements required by the PLN (Persero) of Riau Territory and Riau Islands. At the time of recruitment registration the candidate applies and they themselves choose their field of work. Online registration conditions at www.pln.co.id/riau

2. Endurance Test

The endurance test is an ability to perform continuous physical activity over long periods of time and in an aerobic atmosphere. It is carried out in the recruitment of the executives of the PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands at the level of Senior High School/Vocation Secondary School /Seequal PT PLN/Persero (Riau) Region and the Riau Island, the aim is to know the physical endurance of potential employees such as Push Up, Sit Up, Pull Up, Naik Tower or Height Test.

3. Academic Test

An academic test aimed at identifying a person's talents and abilities in the field of science. (akademis). The PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands in conducting this academic test, namely the Written Test and English Language Test held at the Hotel designated by the Riau Province and Riau Islands, the test is grouped according to the number of participants as well as the schedule that has been determined by the PLN of Riau Territory and Riau Islands.

4. Psychotic test

A psychotic test is a test that is carried out to know by recognizing the personality of potential employees who will work at PT PLN (Persero) as well as knowing and testing potential employees such as IQ tests, psychotics issues such as generally including intelligence, personality tests, people and trees drawing tests and so on. The duration of this test is about three hours. In 2016, the recruitment of senior executives at the level of Senior High School/Vocation Secondary School/Equal Level I PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands in cooperation with the consultancy office of ECC UGM University.

5. Physical and Supportive Health Tests

This health test covers both physical and spiritual because the company will not be able to recruit potential employees whose bodies are healthy but whose spirits are not. Physical health tests are performed such as body height tests, weight tests, balance tests, and doctor's physical tests (such as pressure, teeth, THT, color blindness, pulmonary, anus and gender), feeding tests or laboratory tests such as blood tests, urine tests, heart tests. In this health test, the PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands cooperated with the Laboratories designated by the Riau Province and Riau Islands to carry out health tests, as in 2016 the cooperation of the Prodia Laboratory and Pramita Laboratory in Pekanbaru

6. Interview Test

An interview is a question-and-answer process that takes place between two or more people with the aim of obtaining information based on questions. The interview test carried out in the recruitment of executive staff of PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands to its potential employees is to find out more information from the candidate applicant.

The interviewing officer is an interviewer appointed by the PLN (Persero) office of the Centre who has a Certificate of Competence with the qualification of a competence-based interviewer. Specifications of the problems that occurred during the recruitment of power executive in the PLN (Persero) PT of Riau Territory and Riau Islands.

The obstacles faced during the Recruitment of Employees are:

- a. When the online registration system has an error system, so it controls the slow process on the ground, then the company uses the new system by adjusting it.
- b. Lack of teams on duty at the time of conducting the academic test.

The solutions made by PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands in dealing with the problems faced at the time of recruitment are:

- a. The online registration system is better to use a new system, so that after the day there are no more registration systems that errors.
- b. It's better that the teams that are on duty at the time of the academic test are added so that I don't mistake organizing the participants.

CONCLUSION

In this study the author focuses more on the human resources section about the recruitment process of high school / small and medium-sized / senior executives PT PLN (Persero) Riau Region and Riau Islands from the results of the previous discussion, then the author can conclude that:

1. In the recruitment process of Senior High School / Vocation Secondary School PT PLN (Persero) Riau Territory and Riau Islands has been running well and in accordance with the process passed by the candidate employees until the employees are accepted to become employees of PT PLN (Persero) of Riau Region and Riau Islands.
2. There are still empty posts in the Human Resources Unit of Human Resource Development. This means that there is an unemployed post and the work of the office is done by the employees in the unit so that the company's objectives are not achieved properly and effectively.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bateman, Thomas S. Dkk. 2009. Leadership and Collaboration Management in a Competitive World. Jakarta: Selemba Empat
- Hasibuan, Malayu, S.P., 2013. Human Resource Management. Revised edition. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara
- Kaswan. 2012. Human Resource Management for Organizational Competitive Excellence. First print. Yogyakarta: Graha Science.
- Maribot, Senior Effendi Hariandja. 2009. Human Resource Management, Adjustment, Development, Productivity Improvement of Officers. Jakarta: PT Grasindo
- Mondy, R. Wayne. 2008. Human Resource Management. 10th edition, Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Rachmawati, Ike Kusdyah. 2008. Human Resource Management. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset CV.
- Rivai, Veithzal. 2009. Corporate Management for Companies. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Simamora, Henry. 2010. Human Resource Management. Yogyakarta: STIE.
- Sofyandi, Herman. 2008. Human Resource Management. 1st edition Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Sutrisno, Edi. 2009. Human Resource Management. Print 1. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Wilson. 2012. Human Resource Management. Jakarta: Erlangga.

